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Document Overview

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Glossary

CC BY	Creative Commons Attribution licence
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
DOAB	Directory of Open Access Books
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EPUB	Electronic Book file format
ERC	European Research Council
EU	European Union
FP7	7th Framework Programme
HE	Horizon Europe
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor Identification
PDF	Portable Document Format

Executive summary

The European Union requires all peer-reviewed scientific publications, including books and book chapters, resulting from publicly funded research to be made openly accessible. This policy applies to major research programmes including Horizon Europe, Horizon 2020, 7th Framework Programme (FP7), European Research Council (ERC) grants, and Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA).

To support compliance, the EU has partnered with OAPEN to enable researchers and publishers to use the OAPEN Library to deposit books and chapters funded by EU programmes in line with the EU's Open Science and Open Access mandates.

This report details the guidance for EU researchers and the deposit form that is available on the OAPEN Library webpages.

Introduction

The OAPEN Foundation has been funded for a two-year period to increase and strengthen the dissemination, discoverability, and preservation of Horizon Europe funded books and chapters.

The OAPEN-EU project will develop and maintain a collection of books funded via Horizon Europe, Horizon 2020, 7th Framework Programme (FP7), European Research Council (ERC) grants, and Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) in the OAPEN Library.

This deliverable fulfils part of the project objective to support researchers who are authors of books funded via the Horizon Europe work programmes being compliant with the open access requirements of the European Commission and the European Research Area.

It follows on from earlier activities supported through prior EU-funded initiatives ([ERC-OAPEN-2019 project](#), Grant ID: 964352; and [ERC-OAPEN-2015](#), Grant ID: 683680) focused on the deposit of ERC-funded publications in the OAPEN Library, thereby ensuring continuity and reinforcing the long-term implementation of open access infrastructure for monographs.

OAPEN evaluates the publisher's peer review policy alongside other aspects of the publisher to ensure as best as possible that the publisher will provide books to the OAPEN Library that have undergone rigorous quality control. For these publishers (<https://oapen.org/publishers/publisher-peer-review-policies>) books with Horizon Europe funding will be added to the collection by OAPEN.

However, EU funded authors are free to publish with their chosen publisher, and these publishers may not have their content in the OAPEN Library. A self-service deposit system has been developed for authors to submit books resulting from EU funding directly to the OAPEN collection management team. This impacts the submission rate because authors can fulfil their requirements independent of the publishers.

To increase impact in this way, OAPEN has created a deposit form and provided written guidance for researchers. This guide has been published on the OAPEN Library web pages at (<https://oapen.org/researchers/deposit-your-eu-funded-publication>) and provided in this report below. This report also includes the guidance and text of the self-service deposit form (Appendix 1).

EU-Funded Researchers: Deposit Books in OAPEN for Open Access Compliance

The European Union requires all peer-reviewed scientific publications—including books and book chapters—resulting from publicly funded research to be made openly accessible. This policy applies to major research programmes including [Horizon Europe](#), [Horizon 2020](#), [7th Framework Programme \(FP7\)](#), [European Research Council \(ERC\)](#) grants, and [Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions \(MSCA\)](#).

To support compliance, the EU has partnered with OAPEN, a non-profit platform dedicated to open access books. Researchers and publishers can use the OAPEN Library to deposit books and chapters funded by EU programmes in line with the EU's Open Science and Open Access mandates.

EU Open Access Requirements

Under the EU Open Science policy, researchers must meet five key requirements:

- **Immediate Open Access:** Books and chapters must be available in open access at the time of publication. Embargoes are not allowed.
- **Trusted Repository:** Publications must be deposited in a repository that supports open access, persistent identifiers (e.g., DOI), and long-term preservation. OAPEN qualifies as such a repository.
- **Open Licensing:** A Creative Commons licence (preferably CC BY) must be used, enabling reuse and compliance with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles.
- **Funding Acknowledgement:** The publication must clearly state the EU funding source, including the project acronym, grant number, and funding programme.
- **Metadata:** Standardized, machine-readable metadata must accompany the deposit to enable discoverability and reuse.

These requirements are detailed in Grant Agreement Article 17 (Horizon 2020) and Article 17 of the Model Grant Agreement (Horizon Europe), which outlines beneficiaries' responsibilities for dissemination and open access.

How to Deposit Your EU-Funded Publication

The deposit process is straightforward and can be completed in three steps:

1. First, go to the [OAPEN deposit form](#) to begin your submission.
2. Next, fill out the form with essential information including title, authors, publisher, DOI or ISBN, licensing information (e.g., CC BY), acknowledgement of

EU funding (e.g., “This work was funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No. [XXXXX]”), and upload the open access version of your book or chapter in PDF or EPUB format.

3. Finally, confirm your submission. The OAPEN team will process the deposit and ensure that the publication is included in the dedicated EU Collection, increasing visibility and ensuring compliance and preservation.

Who Can Submit

Authors of EU-funded books or chapters, project coordinators or managers, and publishers acting on behalf of the authors are all eligible to submit. Publishers are encouraged to routinely deposit EU-funded titles to ensure compliance and streamline the process for researchers.

Why Choose OAPEN

OAPEN offers several advantages for EU-funded researchers. It complies fully with EU Open Access mandates, provides long-term hosting and discoverability, and is indexed by major platforms including DOAB and Google Scholar. The OAPEN Library includes a dedicated EU Collection (formerly ERC Collection) and is free for researchers to use, making it an ideal solution for meeting EU compliance requirements while maximizing the impact of your research.

Further Information and Resources

The following resources are available to support you with you OA book publishing journey:

- Read more about the EU’s [support for open access](#).
- View the EU’s [open science policy](#).
- Use the [OAPEN OA Books Toolkit](#) to find out more about self-archiving, choosing an appropriate publisher, and what to look for in your publishing agreement.
- [Think.Check.Submit](#) provides a checklist to help you discover what you need to know when assessing whether or not a publisher is suitable for your research.

Please [contact us](#) if you have any questions.

Appendix 1: EU funded books deposit form

This Appendix shows a text version of the deposit form available at:

<https://operas.atlassian.net/servicedesk/customer/portal/11/group/70/create/194>

Welcome! You can raise a request for EU funded books deposit using the options provided.

Deposit your EU funded book or chapter using this form

Required fields are marked with an asterisk*

Submit Your Publication to the OAPEN Library

Please use this form to submit your monograph or book chapter for inclusion in the OAPEN Library, if it is based on research funded by the European Commission, including European Research Council. We welcome submissions from both authors and publishers.

Each submission should include a PDF or EPUB file, and if you are submitting one or more chapters from a book, please complete a separate form for each chapter.

Full name of contact person*

Email address of contact person*

Publication type*

Book/Chapter

Title*

Add the title of the book or chapter

Subtitle

Author

Add the first author of the title. Use this format: last name, first names. If the ORCID is known, place it behind the name between brackets.

Second author

Do you want to add another author?

Yes/No

Editor

Add the editor of the title. Use this format: last name, first names. If the ORCID is known, place it behind the name between brackets.

Second Editor

Do you want to add another editor?

Yes/No

Publisher*

Add the name of the publisher

DOI

Add the DOI of the book or chapter (if available)

ISBN*

Add all ISBNs of the book, separated by a semicolon

Publication year*

Number of pages

Language*

Select one or more languages

Select...

Abstract*

Keywords*

Add up to 10 keywords, separated by a semicolon

Classification*

Select one or more classifications (THEMA classifications)

Select...

Licence*

Select the open access licence

Please include the funding details to confirm the research was supported by the European Commission.

Funding programme*

Select the funding programme

Grantor*

Select the grantor

Project title*

Add the title of the project as it is known in CORDIS

Project acronym

Add the project acronym as it is known in CORDIS

Grant agreement identifier*

Add the grant agreement identifier as it is known in CORDIS

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